

Further Progress With In Vitro Anther Culture Of European Hazelnut

C. Silvestri, E. Rugini and V. Cristofori

Department of Agriculture and Forestry Sciences (DAFNE), University of Tuscia, Via S. Camillo de Lellis snc, 01100 Viterbo, Italy

Corresponding author: Valerio Cristofori valerio75@unitus.it

Abstract

The fastest way to reach homozygosis is doubling the chromosome number of a haploid genotype. Doubled haploids are useful for fixing traits in desirable combinations, and facilitating marker development, mapping, and marker-assisted selection (MAS). Immature catkins were harvested from branches of selected plants of 'Nocchione', 'Tonda di Giffoni' and 'Tonda Gentile Romana' when the pollen had reached the uninucleate and early bi-nucleate stages. The catkins were surface-sterilized by vigorous shaking in 70% ethanol for 30 seconds, immersion for 10 min in a 20% solution of commercial bleach with a few drops of Tween 20, and washing three times in sterile distilled water. The catkins were stored in sealed plastic bags and maintained for three days at +4 °C in darkness. The anthers were placed on two basal media (N6 and BN) with three combinations of growth regulators. The results confirmed the remarkable influence of the genotype on callus formation. No clear information was obtained, as the analysis of variance revealed a marked interaction among the factors studied. 2,4-D plays a key role in callus formation in hazelnut. No haploid tissues were obtained, although many cells showed chromosome number instability. The better medium and growth regulator combination were identified to induce callus formation from the inner parts of the anthers. This information could be useful for future investigations.

Keywords: *Corylus avellana* L., haploid, growth regulator, pollen, callus formation

INTRODUCTION

The breeding of fruit species is based on conventional (clonal selection, controlled hybridization, mutation) or biotechnological methods employing embryo culture, "in vitro" fertilization, somaclonal variation, somatic hybridization, genetic transformation and haploid production (Germanà et al., 2006; Rugini et al., 2016; Silvestri et al., 2016). Biotechnological techniques are still not used in hazelnut and only a small amount of research has been published on protoplast culture.

Homozygotes are most quickly obtained by doubling the chromosome number of haploids. Doubled haploids are useful to fix traits in desirable combinations, and facilitating marker development, mapping, and marker-assisted selection (MAS). The importance of

haploids in genetic improvement started with the “in vitro” culture of immature anthers of *Datura innoxia*, in which the normal gametophytic development was switched to sporophytic development, inducing somatic embryos with a haploid chromosome number (Germanà, 2011a). The haploid plants from anther culture are usually obtained after surface-sterilization of flowers in sterile conditions followed by anther isolation and culture in liquid or solid media (Sunderland et al., 1984). The most important factors influencing the efficiency of anther culture are the physiological stage and developmental conditions of the donor plants, since they affect the endogenous hormonal content and nutritional status of the anther. Nitrogen starvation conditions often yield embryogenic pollen grains having a large vacuole, few starch grains and a thin exine wall (Heberle-Bors, 1984). Similarly, photoperiod and temperature also influence significantly the embryogenic response of anthers (Heberle-Bors, 1989). Anther culture response is genotype-dependent as described by numerous authors; Bajaj (1990) and Germanà et al. (2007) studied the most responsive cultivar in wheat and citrus, respectively. An anther's “embryogenic period” is from the first mitosis to the bi-cellular stage of pollen development. Anthers rapidly lose their embryogenic capacity when they begin to store starch (Raghavan, 1990; Touarev et al., 2001).

Pre-treatments are also key factors for successful anther culture. The commonly used pre-treatments are cold and heat shocks, starvation of nitrogen and sucrose, chemical treatments, osmotic levels and water stresses (Shariatpanahi et al., 2006). The heat-shock treatment (+41 °C) resulted in acquired embryogenic competence of anthers in rape (Binarova et al., 1997), pepper (Barany et al., 2001) and tobacco (Touarev et al., 1996). Colchicine has been used as stress inducer in various crops such as wheat, maize, rice, sugar beet and sorghum (Germanà, 2011 a, b).

The medium composition plays a key role in anther culture. Gamborg B-5, MS (Murashige and Skoog, 1962) and N6 medium (Chu, 1978) with minor changes are the most used. The MS is mostly employed in solanaceous crops, while N6 has been mostly applied in cereals (Chu, 1978).

The two main functions of growth regulators in anther culture are to induce embryogenesis (Bajaj, 1990; Bajaj et al., 1977) and to identify the fate of embryogenic pathways (Ball et al., 1993). Investigations have demonstrated that 2,4-D promotes and enhances the callus growth, while NAA and IAA are involved in direct embryogenesis (Liang et al., 1987). Also, polyamines can improve the frequency of gametic embryogenesis in clementine (Chiancone et al., 2006), cucumber (Kumar et al., 2004) and wheat (Rajyalakshmi et al., 1995). There are still many species recalcitrant to anther culture, mostly in woody species, as recently reviewed by Dunwell (2010), Germanà (2011a, b), Touarev et al. (2009) and Wedzony et al. (2009). Haploid technology applied to hazelnut was reported by Karasawa et al. (2016). However, further studies are necessary to better understand the process of gametic embryogenesis in this species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Immature catkins were harvested from branches of selected plants of 'Nocchione', 'Tonda di Giffoni' and 'Tonda Gentile Romana' when the pollen reached the uninucleate or early binucleate stage. The catkins were surface-sterilized by vigorous shaking in 70% ethanol for 30 sec, immersing for 10 min in a 20% solution of commercial bleach with a few drops of Tween 20, and washing three times in sterile distilled water. The catkins were stored in sealed plastic bags and maintained in darkness for three days at +4 °C. The catkins were dissected under sterile conditions under a laminar flow hood and the immature anthers were extracted using a needle. The anthers were placed in different media varying

in basal salts and growth regulators. Two basal media, N6 (Chu, 1978) and BN (Bourgin and Nitsch, 1967), supplemented with 3% sucrose and 6% plant agar were used. The pH was adjusted to 5.8 before autoclaving (20 min, +121°C). After sterilization, three different hormone combinations were added: A) 2,4-D 1 mg L⁻¹, IAA 0,5 mg L⁻¹, ZEA 1 mg L⁻¹; B) BAP 2,5 mg L⁻¹, NAA 0,1 mg L⁻¹; C) 2,4-D 1 mg L⁻¹, KIN 1 mg L⁻¹. Forty-eight anthers were placed in each dish and three dishes were prepared for each cultivar and medium. Petri dishes were sealed with parafilm, incubated at +24 ± 1°C for 21 days in the dark and then were subcultured in Petri dishes containing a medium consisting in half-strength MS supplemented with 3% sucrose, IAA 0,5 mg L⁻¹ and TDZ 1 mg L⁻¹, and placed under lights. The numbers of greenish, swollen and callusing anthers were recorded as percentages, and transformed by arcsine square root, and analysis of variance was performed on all data to estimate the effects of cultivars, basal salts and hormone combinations.

Some anther calli were collected and treated with 0.05% colchicine solution for five hours at room temperature. They were then fixed using absolute alcohol : glacial acetic acid (3:1) for 24 hours, hydrolysed in 1N HCl at +60°C for 8 minutes, then stained in 1% acetocarmine solution. A Leitz Dialux 22/22 microscope was used for observations. Data were recorded as percentages, transformed by the arcsin square root, and subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA). The means were separated with Duncan's test (P≤0.01) using R software (<http://cran.rproject.org>).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In anther culture, different features have been described as indicators of the initiation of a morphogenetic response and a change in the developmental pathway. The swelling of anthers has been mentioned as the first anatomical change accompanying the morphogenic response, in contrast to non-responsive anthers which decrease in volume and turgidity (Germanà et al., 2006). Anthers on induction medium appeared greenish after 21 days, with variation among cultivars, basal salts and hormone combinations. The analysis of variance demonstrated significant interactions among the parameters investigated (cultivar x basal salts; cultivar x hormone combinations; basal salts x hormone combinations) (Table 1). In all three cultivars, most of the anthers appeared swollen (Figures 1 b, c) in comparison to the beginning of culture (Figure 1 a). The percentage of swollen anthers seems to be unaffected by the cultivar, but significantly affected by the basal salts. 'Nocchione' showed better results with BN basal salts, while 'Tonda di Giffoni' and 'Tonda Gentile Romana' showed a better response with the N6 basal salts. Furthermore, the hormone combinations significantly affected the percentage of swollen anthers, with the combination 2,4-D 1 mg L⁻¹, IAA 0,5 mg L⁻¹ and ZEA 1 mg L⁻¹ showing the most swollen anthers. A significant interaction between cultivars and hormones was observed (Table 1). Callus formation started from different parts of the anthers, from the external tissues (Figure 1 d) or internal parts of the anthers (Figures 1 e, f), but internal callus formation occurred only in the swollen anthers. In Callus formation incidence in the three cultivars (Table 1) was lowest in 'Tonda Gentile Romana'. In general, BN medium gave a better response than N6 medium (Bourgin and Nitsch, 1967).

Regarding the hormone combinations, 2,4-D 1 mg L⁻¹, IAA 0,5 mg L⁻¹ and ZEA 1 mg L⁻¹ showed the best results, even though not statistically different from the combination of 2,4-D 1 mg L⁻¹ and KIN 1 mg L⁻¹. The combination BAP 2.5 mg L⁻¹ and NAA 0.1 mg L⁻¹ showed the lowest callus induction in all cultivars. Furthermore, the analysis of variance demonstrated a significant interaction among cultivars and hormone combinations, and basal salts x hormone combinations (Table 1). Chromosome observation at 100 × showed no haploid calli in any of the cultivars. However, all of the cells analysed showed high chromosome instability (Figures 2 a, b). Our results confirm the remarkable differences among the genotypes, as reported for many others species. Regarding the basal salts and hormone

combination used, no best combination was identified, since the analysis of variance revealed a marked interaction between the factors studied. Finally, we could speculate that the presence of 2,4-D plays a key role in the callus formation, while the hormone combination of BAP 2.5 mg L⁻¹ and NAA 0.1 mg L⁻¹ appears to be less suitable for callus formation.

CONCLUSIONS

The regeneration of microspore-derived plants or embryos from anthers culture is an important aim in the breeding of fruit crops, particularly for hazelnut, for which biotechnological approaches have been little used to date. There are various factors affecting microspore response, and a deeper knowledge of them may speed up the production of haploids and doubled haploids in hazelnut. Further efforts are necessary to obtain regeneration or embryogenesis from hazelnut anther cultures.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Italian Ministry of Agricultural and Forestry Policy (MIPAAF 2011 – D.D. 17744 “VI.VA.CO. – Sviluppo del vivaismo e della piattaforma varietale corilicola”).

Literature cited

- Bajaj, Y.P.S. (1990). In vitro production of haploids and their use in cell genetics and plant breeding. In: Bajaj YPS (ed) Haploids in crop improvement, vol 12, Biotechnology in agriculture and forestry. Springer, Berlin, pp 1–44.
- Bajaj, Y.P.S., Reinert, J., and Heberle, E. (1977). Factors enhancing in vitro production of haploid plants in anthers and isolated microspores. In: Gautheret RJ (ed) La culture des tissus et des cellules des vegetaux. Masson, Paris, pp 47–58.
- Ball, S.T., Zhou, H.P., and Konzak, C.F. (1993). Influence of 2,4-D, IAA, and duration of callus induction in anther cultures of spring wheat. *Plant Sci.*, 90(2):195–200.
- Barany, I., Testillano, P.S., Mityko, J., and Risueno, M.C. (2001). The switch of the microspore developmental programme in *Capsicum* involves HSP70 expression and leads to the production of haploid plants. *Int J Dev Biol.*, 45:39–40.
- Binarova, P., Hause, G., Cenklova, V., Cordewener, J.H.G., and Campagne, M.M.V. (1997). A short severe heat shock is required to induce embryogenesis in late bicellular pollen of *Brassica napus* L. *Sex Plant Reprod.*, 10(4):200–208.
- Bourgin, J.P. and Nitsch, J.P. (1967). Obtention de *Nicotiana* haploïdes à partir d'étamines cultivées in vitro (Production of haploid *Nicotiana* from excised stamen). *Ann. Physio. Veg.*, 9: 377–382.
- Chiancone, B., Tassoni, A., Bagni, N., and Germana, M.A. (2006). Effect of polyamines on in vitro anther culture of *Citrus clementina* Hort. ex Tan. *Plant Cell Tissue Organ Cult.*, 87(2):145–153.
- Chu, C.C. (1978). The N6 medium and its application to anther culture of cereal crops. *Proc. Symp. Plant Tissue Cult.*, Peking, 43.
- Dunwell, J.M. (2010). Haploids in flowering plants: origins and exploitation. *Plant Biotechnol J.*, 8(4):377–424.
- Gamborg, O.L., Miller R.A., and Ojima K. (1968). Nutrient requirement of suspensions cultures of soybean root cells. *Exp. Cell. Res.*, 20,151.
- Germanà, M.A., Chiancone, B., Guarda, N.L., Testillano, P.L., and Risueno, M.C. (2006). Development of multicellular pollen of *Eriobotrya japonica* Lindl. through anther culture. *Plant Science.*, 171:718–725.
- Germanà, M.A. (2011a). Anther culture for haploid and doubled haploid production. *Plant Cell Tissue Organ Cult.*, 104(3):283–300.
- Germanà, M.A. (2011b). Gametic embryogenesis and haploid technology as valuable support to plant breeding. *Plant Cell Rep.*, 30(5):839–857.
- Germanà, M. A., Ahmad, H. I., Maurizio, M., and Alvaro, S. (2007). Preliminary research on conversion of encapsulated somatic embryos of citrus *reticulata* blanco, cv. mandarino tardivo di ciaculli. *Plant Cell, Tissue and Organ Culture*, 88(1), 117–120
- Heberle-Bors, E. (1984). Pollen embryogenesis a model system for the life cycle of higher plants. *J Embryol Exp Morphol.*, 82(suppl):17.
- Heberle-Bors, E. (1989). Isolated pollen culture in tobacco: plant reproductive development in a nutshell. *Sex Plant Reprod.*, 2(1):1–10.

- Karasawa, M.M.G., Chiancone, B., Gianguzzi, V., Abdelgalel, A.M., Botta, R., Sartor, C., and Germanà, M.A. (2016). Gametic embryogenesis through isolated microspore culture in *Corylus avellana* L. *Plant Cell Tissue Organ Cult.*, 124(3):635–647
- Kumar, H.G.A., Ravishankar, B.V., and Murthy, H.N. (2004). The influence of polyamines on androgenesis of *Cucumis sativus* L. *Eur J Horti Sci.*, 69(5):201–205.
- Liang, G.H., and Xu, A. (1987). Direct generation of wheat haploids via anther culture. *Crop Sci.*, 27(2):336–339.
- Murashige, T., and Skoog, F. (1962). A revised medium for rapid growth and bioassays with tobacco tissue cultures. *Physiology Plant.*, 473-497.
- Raghavan, V. (1990). From microspore to embryoid - faces of the angiosperm pollen grain, vol 9. *Progress in plant cellular and molecular biology.* Kluwer Academic, Dordrecht.
- Rajyalakshmi, K., Chowdhry, C.N., Maheshwari, N., and Maheshwari, S.C. (1995). Anther culture response in some Indian wheat cultivars and the role of polyamines in induction of haploids. *Phytomorphology*, 45(1–2):139–145.
- Rugini, E., Cristofori, V., and Silvestri, C. (2016). Genetic improvement of olive (*Olea europaea* L.) by conventional and in vitro biotechnology methods. *Biotechnology Advances*, 34: 687-696.
- Shariatpanahi, M.E., Bal, U., Heberle-Bors, E., and Touraev, A. (2006). Stresses applied for the re- programming of plant microspores towards in vitro embryogenesis. *Physiol Plant*, 127(4):519–534.
- Silvestri, C., Cristofori, V., Ceccarelli, M., Caceres, M. E., Escribã -Lacuesta, J., and Rugini, E. (2016). Adventitious shoot organogenesis from leaf and petiole explants of european hazelnut. *Plant Cell, Tissue and Organ Culture*, 126(1), 59-65. doi:10.1007/s11240-016-0976-7
- Sunderland, N., Huang, B., and Hills, G.J. (1984). Disposition of pollen insitu and its relevance to anther pollen culture. *J Exp Bot.*, 35(153):521–530.
- Touraev, A., Forster, B.P., and Jain, S.M. (2009). *Advances in haploid production in higher plants.* Springer, Dordrecht.
- Touraev, A., Pfosser, M., Vicente, O., and Heberle-Bors, E. (1996). Stress as the major signal controlling the developmental fate of tobacco microspores: towards a unified model of induction of microspore/pollen embryogenesis. *Planta*, 200(1):144–152.
- Touraev, A., Pfosser, M., and Heberle-Bors, E. (2001). The microspore: a haploid multipurpose cell. *Adv Bot Res.*, 35:53–109.
- Wedzony, M., Forster, B.P., Zur, I., Golemic, E., Szechynska-Hebda, M., Dubas, E., and Gotebiowska, G. (2009). Progress in doubled haploid technology in higher plants. In: Touraev, A., Forster, B.P., Jain, S.M. (eds). *Advances in haploid production in higher plants.* Springer, Dordrecht, pp 1–33.

Tables

Table 1: Anther culture in *Corylus avellana* L. 'Nocchione', 'Tonda di Giffoni' and 'Tonda Romana', in different induction media. Analysis of variance was performed

Cultivar	Basal salts	Hormone Treatments	Green anthers (%)	Swollen anthers (%)	Callus formation (%)
Nocchione	BN	A	55	82	67
	N6-CHU	A	80	82	39
	BN	B	16	55	11
	N6-CHU	B	5	33	19
	BN	C	36	50	55
	N6-CHU	C	86	80	41
Tonda di Giffoni	BN	A	72	62	77
	N6-CHU	A	95	76	40
	BN	B	30	26	9
	N6-CHU	B	17	57	7
	BN	C	68	56	24
	N6-CHU	C	52	77	50
Tonda Gentile Romana	BN	A	25	49	42
	N6-CHU	A	85	75	13
	BN	B	24	49	0
	N6-CHU	B	7	64	0
	BN	C	14	43	4
	N6-CHU	C	3	44	5
Factors			P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01
Cultivar (cv)			**	n.s.	**
Basal Salts (bs)			**	**	**
Hormones (h)			**	**	**
cv x bs			*	n.s.	n.s.
cv x h			**	*	**
bs x h			**	n.s.	**
cv x bs x h			**	*	**

Figures

Figure 1: Anther culture of 'Nocchione' hazelnut: a) undeveloped anthers; b), c) swollen anthers; d) callus formation from external tissues of anther; e), f) callus formation from internal tissues of anthers.

Figure 2: Chromosomes in cells of calli derived from 'Nocchione' hazelnut anthers. No haploid cells were found, but all cells showed high chromosome instability (a, b).